

For an Art Against the Cartography of Everyday Life

Simply put, everyday life might be the name for the desire of totality in postmodern times.¹

We should now talk of people making not their own history but their own geography.²

This text is a limited exploration of some relatively recent cultural practices that are connected in various ways to issues of geography and technology, what has been called a "spatial turn" in some academic circles, and a "locative turn" in the telecom industries and the niche art market commonly known as "new media". In particular, I'd like to read these practices, frequently referred to as "locative media," and the discourse that surrounds them, through previous critical frameworks that have engaged with notions of "the everyday" and the formal language of documentary image making. My intention is to arrive at more questions than answers through this mediation, as it comes from conflicting positions of both distrust in, and desire for, the utopian aspirations driving much of this turn to the spatial in cultural production.

1 Ben Highmore, *Everyday Life and Cultural Theory*, Routledge, 2002

2 John Urry, "Social Relations, Space and Time" in *Spatial Relations and Spatial Structures*, Derek Gregory and John Urry Ed, MacMillan Publishers Ltd, 1985

My title is a remix of another title used by the artist Martha Rosler for a text originally published in 1979, "For an Art Against the Mythology of Everyday Life".³ Rosler's text is an engagement with what was then the emerging context now often referred to as "post-industrial globalization." More specifically, it is an engagement from the perspective of someone attempting to make things - art works - that can "address these banally profound issues of everyday life, thereby revealing the public and political in the personal". She was particularly interested in both the oppressive and potentially liberating aspects of "mass media." I want to take up Rosler's challenge for art and technology to "step toward reasonably and humanely changing the world" in terms of some current cultural work.

Locative Media has been used to refer to both commercial and "critical" avant garde applications of geospatially aware technologies. Both often share a predilection for revealing the individual experience of "everyday life" and connecting it to larger, socially mediated and networked forms of experience. Locative media relies on the placement and movement of devices that can compute, and then transmit, their location to other, equally connected devices, like computers. In a larger cultural sphere, this is visible in the proliferation of the Geographic Positioning System (GPS) technology that is becoming increasingly common in devices like cell phones and automobiles. Such

³ "For an Art Against the Mythology of Everyday Life" Rosler, Martha. Republished in *Decoys and Disruptions: Selected Writings, 1975–2001*, MIT Press, 2004.

connectivity starts to collapse the conventional distance between inhabited space and the virtual space of cartography, as the scale of the map begins to correspond with inhabited, terrestrial scales. Locative media benefits from such deployment of communication technologies as "ubiquitous" - to be everywhere, at all times, and often unnoticed and inaccessible. Such notions of ubiquity can't help but intersect with notions of "the everyday" - where else is "the everyday" if not in "the everywhere"?

Commercial applications that illustrate this include mobile phone software applications like Earthcomber, Mobio and Mologogo that give subscribers knowledge about their surroundings, such as restaurant reviews and nightlife suggestions.⁴ More inventive applications, such as Dodgeball, offer to extend friend-of-a-friend networks in real-time by sending a text message to you anytime someone in your social network is nearby, functioning like a mobile version of Myspace or Facebook. And of course, for those of us who are not early adopters of such portable technologies, the rise of web-based mapping tools, from Mapquest, Google, Amazon, Microsoft and Yahoo! that allow for amateur development has produced a massively experiential link between spatial cartography and everyday existence, at least for those of us with broadband.

⁴ see Higgins, Michelle, "A Guide to Anywhere, Right in Your Hand," New York Times, June 17, 2007

Rosler begins "For an Art Against the Mythology of Everyday Life" with the question, "Where do ideas come from?".⁵ She immediately answers her question with, "All the myths of everyday life stitched together form a seamless envelope of ideology, the false account of the workings of the world." It is her understanding of "the everyday" as an ideological construction that I find useful in interrogating current work in locative media. Notions of "the everyday" as a site of resistance, dissent and creativity have been celebrated for their embodiment of what Michel deCerteau referred to as "tactics".⁶ This somewhat ludic and utopian depiction of "making do" in the face of regimes of power, however, can equally serve to reinforce the "myths of everyday life" Rosler is trying to make knowable. The condition of always acting tactically requires a constant state of sublimation and reactionary posturing, that while potentially liberating in the face of short term oppression, can never respond adequately to inequities.

The process of knowledge creation is described by geographer Nigel Thrift as both an additive and subtractive process, where processes of "unknowing" play an equally important role in the distribution and re/production of knowledge.⁷ Thrift's classification of knowing and unknowing, as well as his depiction of "situated social action", represents an attempt to imagine how what is not known - whether it is simply

⁵Rosler, 1979/2004 p.3

⁶ de Certeau, Michel, *The Practice of Everyday Life*, University of California Press, 1984.

⁷ Thrift, Nigel, "Flies and Germs," *Social Relations and Spatial Structures*, Derek Gregory and John Urry, Editors, MacMillan Publishers, 1985.

outside of one's experience or just distorted - contributes to "how ideologies are represented and diffused in the relatively untheoretical 'ways of life'".⁸ I am interested here in how this framework for understanding knowledge and its distribution can be employed to analyze the practice of locative media, as an interface to knowledge that can seal, as well as open, the "seamless envelope of ideology".

So where do these ideas most directly intersect with the activities and products I've set out to explore? On the commercial side, it's about making the ideological link between life and consumption even more seamless than before. The same tools we use to communicate with loved ones become tools for consumer decision making. The utopian desire for this is represented by the image of an endless network of consumers, newly empowered to publicly share their experiences and encounters with products and places. The middle-men of advertising and public relations become obsolete in the face of peer-reviewed consumption. But this assumes an otherwise level playing field, where access to information technologies is evenly distributed and desires are based on rational needs and healthy relationships. Even a shallow look at what and how these technologies are developing presents a worldview that are perhaps not as novel as their high tech aesthetics of interactivity suggest. Take for example, the popularity of mapping applications that facilitate commercial real estate transactions, such as

⁸ Thrift, p. 396

HousingMaps.com that connects Craigslist real estate listings and Google Maps. The following statement from Thai Tran, a Google Maps product manager, commenting on the release of a new panoramic, photo-based interface by Google, is revealing as it clearly identifies the concerns driving such services and technologies:

One day we were looking at two of the original Google Maps mashups, HousingMaps.com and ChicagoCrime.org, and we realized it would be even more useful if they could be combined because most people wouldn't want to live near high crime areas.⁹

In Tran's statement, we find that, for all the new technologically-facilitated "communities" we can now create, they don't look all that different from those divided by red-lines, created by earlier generations of GIS applications.¹⁰ The technologies may have progressed, but our desires arguably haven't all that much. I will return to some of the implications of this technological inscription of desire later, but would like to shift into a discussion of locative media as it is practiced and celebrated within the avant garde cultural sphere, and more specifically, in contemporary art.

⁹ quoted in Mills, Elinor, "Google Maps Takes it to the Streets," C-Net News.com, May 29, 2007. http://news.com.com/Google+Maps+takes+it+to+the+streets/2100-1038_3-6187254.html

¹⁰ Cloud, John, "American Cartographic Transformations during the Cold War," *Cartography and Geographic Information Science*, Vol. 29, No. 3, 2002, pp.261-282.

One contemporary locative media art work that has received much attention is a mapping project by Esther Polak, Ieva Auzina and the Riga Center for New Media Culture (RIXC) titled "MILK."¹¹ Completed from 2003 through 2005, "MILK" follows the production and distribution of cheese, from Latvian dairy farms to the markets of Utrecht. Following the movements of nine "participants" (selected people involved in the making, moving and consumption of cheese) through the use of GPS devices given to them, "MILK" proposes to give us a glimpse into the social, and spatial, construction of cheese. The self-generated press for the project positions it as a "locative art - mapping project, that explores visual and documenting possibilities of GPS technology."¹²

The project's basic components consist of some text, video and photographic imagery that records the movements of farmers, dealers and buyers of cheese. Through these mediations, the artists represent the spatial histories and knowledges that are, for all practical purposes, otherwise inaccessible and invisible in the material of cheese.

"MILK" re-presents "cheese" as a body of knowledge that can be engaged on a human

11 MILK was awarded the 2005 Golden Nica Award at Ars Electronica and exhibited in Bruno Latour and Peter Weibel's "Making Things Public" at the ZKM in Karlsruhe, Germany.

12 From the artist's statement online <http://www.milkproject.net/press/press9.html> accessed 04/13/07

See Marc Tuter's analysis of the utopian potential of locative media, which he finds specifically present in "MILK" and terms "awaretarianism" for its potential to insert awareness through affect into the consumption and production process. Tuters, Marc, "The Locative Utopia," Transcultural Mapping Reader, <http://locative.net/tcmreader/index.php?endo;tuters>, accessed 04/13/07

scale, through the actions and thoughts of those involved in its production, and on a more macro scale, through visualizations that reveal the geographic distances and time involved in its materialization.

Not surprising, one of the primary influences in the creation of the project, stated by Esther Polak, was the artist's recollection of an earlier documentary project of rural life, poet James Agee and photographer Walker Evans' 1941 account of poor farmers in the US South, "Let Us Now Praise Famous Men."¹³ Evans' and Agee's project, begun as an assignment for Fortune Magazine in 1936, is in many ways a classic example of New Deal era documentary work, combining the aesthetic sensibilities of the two artists with the Progressive political values of the emerging welfare state. As Polak and other commentators on "Let Us Now Praise Famous Men" have noted, the book is both celebrated and criticized for its "experimental" or "difficult" method of combining text and pictures. Polak goes so far as to call it a "technological experiment," echoing other common impressions of the work as "challenging" and rejecting "any vision of the world as clearly understandable and ordered."¹⁴ This reading of Agee and Evans' collaboration provides Polak, and her perceived audience, with a precedent for MILK - the creation of an experimental, yet universalizing, narrative of the everyday existence of rural

13 <http://www.beelddiktee.nl/projects/GPS-projects/milk/Artist-statement-EP-eng.htm>

14 Coogle, Matt, "The Historical Significance of Let Us Now Praise Famous Men," The Hanover Historical Review, Vol. 1, Spring 1993. http://history.hanover.edu/hhr/hhr93_6.html

farmers. Both share the familiar documentary aim of making visible for their audience the stories of marginalized people and places.

This identification with documentary should not be surprising, but should also not give undue import to the artists' intentions. It does, however, provide a lens through which to view the materialization of meanings that locative media represents, meanings that, I argue, can be productively read as a further development in documentary image making. It is important to note that while some instances of locative media are more easily relatable to documentary traditions, such as "MILK," other locative practices don't begin or end with those traditions.

Where locative media practitioners and proponents can point to the difference between their work and conventional documentary practice is in their desire and ability to annotate space - to link their narratives to specific, geographic contexts. Many locative media projects use geo-spatial technology to attach stories, sound and relationships to locations such that an intersection between virtual/networked space and geographic space can be used to visualize invisible or imaginary realities. Projects like Yellow Arrow, Tactical Sound Garden, and [murmur], just to name a few, primarily situate themselves as revisions to the spaces they occupy - rather than documenting a singular history, they attempt to generate new experiences or reveal stories that are somehow not

already present. [murmur], for example, produces audio stories about specific locations, and uses stickers marked with phone numbers to provide access to those stories for people inhabiting those very spaces. Like many similar projects, [murmur] is an attempt to activate space with generally inaccessible historical texts, to "change the way people think about that place" by bringing "that important archive out onto the streets."¹⁵

Likewise, another trope within locative media practice is what I would call the augmentation of space - the imaginary and/or technological transposition of one space upon another. This trope is usually related to the earlier, and now fashionable, Lettrist and Situationist practice of the psychogeographic derive, where a map of one location may be used to navigate the space of another. Contemporary examples of such work include "You Are Not Here", in which a group of NYU Information Technology Program created an audio tour of Baghdad, Iraq in the space of New York City. In a similar manner, spatial augmentations are used to create a kind of expanded game space, for example projecting the conceptual terrain of Pac-Man onto the architectural grid of Manhattan.¹⁶

Despite the methodology of annotating and imagining spaces manifest in these projects, I would argue that they function in a manner not totally foreign to traditional

¹⁵ <http://murmurtoronto.ca/about.php>

¹⁶ Pac-Manhattan is the project referenced here, also the product of the NYU ITP program.

documentary practice. In many respects, I can find in contemporary locative media practices a response to critiques of archival and documentary models, by Rosler and others, like artist and theorist Alan Sekula. [murmur]'s creation of an alternative archive of Toronto, for example, could be read as an answer to Sekula's dictum that "the archive has to be read from below, from a position of solidarity with those displaced, deformed, silenced, or made invisible by the machineries of profit and progress."¹⁷ Recent cinematic documentaries have likewise taken to forms that attempt to transfer agency to the traditional subject of documentary investigations, as in recent films like "The War Tapes," in which US soldiers in Iraq were given cameras with which to document their experiences.

Importantly, however, Sekula's call for critical action is not solely based on the "content" of the archive - the collective and individual stories are only part of the picture.

Referring to the oft-quoted Walter Benjamin truism that all documents of civilization are simultaneously documents of barbarism, Sekula is careful to include the full target of Benjamin's words:

"And just as such a document is not free of barbarism, barbarism taints also the manner in which it was transmitted from one owner to another."¹⁸

17 Sekula, Alan, "Reading an Archive," *Blasted Allegories*, Brian Wallis, Ed., MIT Press, 1987, p.128

18 *ibid.*

If locative media purports to provide tools for the creation and reception of counter-archives, providing access to the very means of knowledge (and therefore historical) production, this indeed seems an emancipatory shift toward self-representation. But the means through which locative media operates should also be considered. In recent debates about the cultural capital that locative media has been attracting, critiques leveled against its most visible instances have accused it of complicity with capitalist spectacle and, worse, as cultural research and development for surveillance and data mining industries. Many have attacked this complicity and the historical connections between contemporary technologies of geographic visualization and the US military.¹⁹

On the one hand, the significance of location-based media art can be critically analyzed through the established framework of representation; using the tools of cultural and visual studies, we can arrive at a reading of how the content of locative media fits into, or ruptures, the current paradigms of meaning, signification and knowledge production. As Anne Galloway and Matthew Ward have shown, we can see locative media as an extension of "representational technologies," as "ultimately understood as collections of cultural artifacts."²⁰

19 See an archive of some of these discussions here: <http://www.turbulence.org/blog/archives/000493.html> with contributions by artist Coco Fusco and new media theorists Armin Medosch, Brian Holmes, Drew Hemment and Andreas Brockman

20 Galloway, Anne and Matthew Ward, "Locative Media as Socialising and Spatialising Practices: Learning from Archaeology (Draft)", 2005. http://www.purselipssquarejaw.org/papers/galloway_ward_draft.pdf. See also Marc Tuters and Kazys Varnelis' "Beyond Locative Media," http://www.netpublics.annenberg.edu/locative_media/beyond_locative_media. All accessed 04/13/07.

But this would be only looking at locative media as a mechanism of representation, without consideration of the affective qualities of the technology itself. Without ignoring the importance of representation, and avoiding a reductive technological determinist analysis, we can look at the manner in which locative media could be read through Gilles Deleuze's notion of a "control society" in which access and mobility are designed into systems, rather than enforced through disciplinary means.²¹ This reading might, for example, begin with the material history of Geographic Information Systems (GIS), the mapping of quantifiable, spatial information about populations and environments, with its origins in the combination of Cold War era MGIS (Military Geographic Information Systems) and earlier forms of mapping the urban housing crisis during the Great Depression, and even earlier examples such as John Snow's mid 19th Century delineation of a London cholera outbreak.²² Along with the mapping of Communist threats, GIS became a valuable tool in the ongoing domestic wars against the urban poor under the guise of "urban renewal," dissecting cities with highways and other forms of what Mike Davis has referred to as "third borders."²³ In this light, contemporary geo-tracking tools can be seen as part of what geographer Stephen Graham calls "software-sorted geographies," where the sorting of social privileges is

21 Gilles Deleuze, "Postscript on the Societies of Control", *OCTOBER* 59, Winter 1992, MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, pp. 3–7.

22 Cloud pp.261–282.

23 Davis, Mike, "Policing the Third Border," *Colorlines*, Issue 6, Fall 1999

achieved not through enforcement of compliance, but rather through a preemptive selection of allowable conditions achieved through the employment of regulatory software in spaces of potential conflict.²⁴ Just as walls and massive highways can serve to regulate movements between regions of a city, software, when connected to mechanical access points, can be used to regulate access to transportation, buildings and services.

The barbarism found in the means of transmission, here the network of technologies linking knowledge and space, can be read as well as that of the symbolic meaning being transmitted. The melding of knowledge and space requires the simultaneous fusing of that knowledge with privileges of mobility and technological access. Mediated space becomes an archive, not of political contestation, but of narratives accessible only to those who benefit from voluntary processes of surveillance. This is not the panoptic surveillance of Foucault's disciplinary society, it is the surveillance of supermarket value cards, toll-road EZ passes, automobile GPS tracking systems and biometric airline regulation.²⁵ There is little need to surveil those on the "outside" of the system.

24 Graham, Stephen, "Software-sorted Geographies," *Progress in Human Geography* 29, 5, 2005, pp. 1–19.

25 The efforts of the United States and some Western EU nations to implement various forms of biometric and digital regulation of travelers has shown up a lot in the press over the last few years. A recent proposal by segments of the US Congress to regulate more aggressively travelers from certain EU countries is just the most recent example. Knowlton, Brian, "U.S. proposals on visa rules raise fears in Europe," *International Herald Tribune*, June 15, 2007. See also the development of both national and private security initiatives that serve only to increase the mobility of selected segments of the population, such as the SENTRI program on the US-Mexico border and the commercial Clear Card program.

This is where the usefulness of reading locative media within the histories of documentary practice would seem to become questionable, if there weren't counter examples of locative media that take into consideration equally their relationship with mechanisms of control, and the practice of social documentary. The Italian collective Multiplicity provide one such instance of location awareness through which geographies of inequity can be visualized and experienced. For "Road Map," the collective made two journeys of similar distance, through Israeli and Palestinian-controlled territories, one time using an Israeli passport, the other time a Palestinian one. These two journeys were mapped and recorded with video, documenting the disparity in duration between the trips - roughly one hour with the Israeli passport, and over five hours with the Palestinian papers. Opposed to the view of space presented by MILK's GPS derived drawings on pixelated, abstracted renderings of Europe, what Michael Curry has called a "view from nowhere," "Road Map" presents an understanding of space as inextricable from the systems that shape it.²⁶ There is no neutral ground upon which to project narrative movements, only a ground delineated with checkpoints and regulated zones for some and by-pass roads for others. There is not one map, but (at least) two.

26 Curry, Michael, *Digital Places: Living with Geographic Information Technology*, Routledge, 1998, p.52.

This disorientation and instability that can result from people making their own geography was the focus of a 1995 work by architect and artist Laura Kurgan titled "You Are Here: Museu," that took place at the Museu d'Art Contemporani de Barcelona. With "You Are Here" Kurgan used a combination of static and mobile GPS devices to reveal a slippage in the precision and stability of GPS technology. GPS, a system of 24 satellites and control stations owned by the United States and operated by the US Airforce, allows mobile devices to determine their precise location on the Earth, with some built in limitations and distortions. By placing a static GPS device on the roof of the Museu, and recording the constantly updating readings of its position, Kurgan visualized the difference between the space produced by GPS and the space upon which the Museu stood. GPS, Kurgan concludes, is "not a representation of a space, but a space itself... a space in which we think and act and move, every day."²⁷ Walking on the roof with another GPS device, the Catalan word "Museu" was spelled out, revealing that the coordinates of the points and lines that are read as language do not even fall within the boundaries of the Museu itself. Kurgan's "charting of the spaces that chart the spaces" proposes that we, in fact, read "these computerized spaces as real spaces, at least as real as anything else."

²⁷ <http://www.l00k.org/?s=youarehere> accessed 04/13/07.

Acknowledging the shifting boundaries between the space we consider inhabitable and these computerized spaces, the notion that we are moving through the space created by satellites and control centers, miles away from our perceived location, becomes thinkable. And if we can move through these spaces, our movements can likewise be regulated by them. And just as they become part of established conceptions of "the everyday," they likewise alter the boundaries of knowledge, either opening or sealing the envelope of ideology further. New Media theorist Drew Hemment has suggested that locative media might be better termed "embedded media" in recognition of its "inherent complicity in the operation of power," referring, of course, to the recent practice of journalists being "embedded" with the US military.²⁸ This notion of an "embedded" locative media turns citizens into prosumers (the popular neologism referring to productive consumers) of locatable content, content that is designed as much to analyze their movements and habits as it is to entertain or educate. One might say the King's minions have taken it upon themselves to write a contemporary Domesday Book themselves. Only the King isn't such a simple entity anymore, but is rather some messy chimera of state and corporate interests who feed on data as much as taxes.

28 Hemment, Drew, "The Locative Dystopia," <http://makeworlds.net/node/76>, February 21, 2004.

It seems important to ask if it is sufficient merely to acknowledge complicity, to accept the dialectical utopian/dystopian visions. In another text on documentary and photography, Rosler questions representations of power that defy causal analysis:

"If there are no victims - or if, what amounts to the same thing, we are all equally victims - then there are no oppressors. Social inequality appears to be produced by a system without active human agents or collective remedies. ...in the present map of the world, the self-same photo might simply be readable as an image of the random Brownian motion of individuals present in the same unit of space-time, and adding up only to numbers, not to 'society.'"²⁹

Technology may further mediate power and control, and in many senses may even physically embody them, but does technology replace ideology? Does perspective collapse under the unseen mass of 24 satellites? Michael Curry suggests that the "view from nowhere" always and already occupies a position of interest, but that perspective becomes located further and further from the place of power - in this case, literally in space.³⁰ If the tendency of the control society is to embed ideology into mechanisms of domination, essentially black-boxing oppression, how can the black box be opened and its contents documented? Or do we have to wait for a crash before it can be recovered?

²⁹ Rosler p177.

³⁰ Curry p.52